

TIME-INCLINED METHOD VALIDATION IN A TURBOMACHINERY HIGH-ORDER
SOLVER

Roque Corral*

Universidad Politecnica de Madrid
28040 Madrid, Spain
e-mail: roque.corral@upm.es

Miguel Montiel†

Universidad Politecnica de Madrid
28040 Madrid, Spain
e-mail: m.montiel@upm.es

Fernando Gisbert

Industria de Turbopropulsores S.A.U.
28108 Alcobendas, Spain
e-mail: fernando.gisbert@itpaero.com

ABSTRACT

This work demonstrates for the first time the application of the Time-Inclined (TI) method in a 4th order unstructured flux-reconstruction time-marching code for turbomachinery applications. The inviscid and viscous unsteady results, due to the interaction of a high-frequency incoming gust of total pressure with firstly a linear cascade of flat plates and secondly, a linear cascade of T106 low-pressure turbine airfoils are reported. It is shown that the agreement between the single-passage time-inclined and the equivalent full-annulus multi-passage solution is very high, both for the flat plate and the T106 cascades. Viscous solutions at Reynolds number 100,000 based on the chord have been conducted as well. It is demonstrated that the degree of matching between the time-inclined and the full-annulus solutions is very high as well, at least up to the first harmonic of the blade passing frequency.

NOMENCLATURE

c	Airfoil or plate chord
a_0	Speed of sound
DOF	Degrees Of Freedom
\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{g}	Convective fluxes in the x and y direction
\mathbf{F}, \mathbf{G}	Viscous fluxes in the x and y direction
FR	Flux Reconstruction
h	Stream-tube height
k	Reduced frequency
L	Lagrange polynomial
LPT	Low-Pressure Turbine
p	Pressure
P	Pitch of the airfoil
PP	Physical Plane
\mathbf{Q}	$= \mathbf{U} - \lambda \mathbf{g}$, Time-inclined variables
RANS	Reynolds-Average Navier-Stokes
Re	$= \rho v_{e,isc} c / \mu$, Reynolds number
\mathbf{S}	Source term
SP	Solution Point
TI	Time-Inclined
t	Time
\mathbf{U}	Vector of conservative variables
V	Wheel speed
x, y	Cartesian coordinates

Greek symbols

γ	Correction flux
ξ, η	Element coordinates

*Professor of Aerospace Engineering, Department of Fluid Mechanics and Aerospace Propulsion, Universidad Politécnica Madrid

†Corresponding Author

ω	Blade passing frequency
τ	Shear stress tensor

Super-scripts

C	Continuous
D	Discontinuous
I	Interface
'	Transformed coordinate

Sub-scripts

e	Exit
is	Isentropic
r	Rotor
s	stator
0	Total or stagnation conditions

INTRODUCTION

Scale resolving simulations have evolved up to a point in which they can compete with low Technology Readiness Level (TRL) experiments [1, 2]. The fine scales are resolved properly, often without any type of modelling, and the computational cost is affordable at the industrial level for quasi three-dimensional simulations at moderate Reynolds numbers ($Re \sim 10^5$) provided that they are restricted to a single-passage. However, long spatial scales associated with the blade count disparity between stators and rotors can play a significant role making convenient to retain the exact blade count of the airfoil and its perturbations in eddy resolving simulations.

Virtual experiments reproducing linear cascades with moving bars are beginning to become commonplace [3, 4, 5, 1, 2] but frequently the accuracy of the simulations is compromised to accommodate the blade count to a single passage. For instance, in the experiment reported by Bolinches et al. [2], the true ratio between the pitch of the rotating bars and the airfoils was $P_r/P_s = 1.07$ but it was approximated to $P_r/P_s = 1$ in the simulations. Moreover, the bar speed was adjusted to match the bar passing frequency changing the experimental flow parameter. For realistic blade counts, this is not an option and this approach contradicts performing computationally intensive high-fidelity simulations since at the same time the physical parameters of the simulations are approximated grossly.

One of the main bottlenecks for a generalised application of high-fidelity simulations in the industry lies in the difficulties encountered when the stator/rotor pitch ratio is not a small integer ratio. In this case, spatial periodicity is only recovered including a large number of blade-passages in the computational domain reducing significantly the affordability of the simulations.

Several methods have been proposed in the past to deal with dissimilar blade counts using a single-passage approach. (author?) [6] addressed for the first time the problem of the computational efficiency of a stator/rotor interaction with dissimilar pitches between the stator and the rotor (see Fig. ?? (a)) using a method whereby the solution was reconstructed in the periodic

boundaries and the sliding plane assuming that the solution was periodic in time. This approach was refined approximating the stored solution by a truncated Fourier series in time to reduce the amount of storage [7, 8], and to account for multiple fundamental frequencies [9].

The strongest hypothesis of the aforementioned methods is that the harmonic content of the flow is formed by a few fundamental frequencies associated to the blade passing frequencies of the neighbouring rows and its higher-order harmonics [9]. This hypothesis is needed to reconstruct the signal using earlier time-instants on the opposite side of the periodic line. Temporal signals coming from scale-resolving rotor/stator simulations superimpose random-like unsteady contributions to a baseline URANS-like periodic content of the signal, conceptually preventing a direct application of phase-lagged boundary conditions, though recent attempts have been pursued with little success [10, 11].

The use of phase-shifted boundary conditions suffers from two additional problems. The first is a degradation of the convergence time with respect to the full-annulus simulation. This is true even for a URANS simulation. Part of this problem stems from the difficulty in implementing fully consistent phase-lag boundary conditions in the periodic boundaries. To remedy this problem, Biesinger et al. [12] proposed the dual-passage method whereby the phase-lagged boundary conditions are implemented in two-passages instead of a single one to speed-up the convergence problem. Giovannini et al. [13] reported a factor of five in computational time using this technique in a rotor/stator simulation despite using twice as many points as the original method. Moreover, in a scale resolving simulation, the time spectrum is richer than in URANS simulations, and the number of snapshots that need to be stored in the boundaries is very high.

Giles [14, 15] introduced in the early nineties the use of time-inclined computational planes to deal with the difficulties encountered with dissimilar stator/rotor pitch ratios. The time-inclined (TI) method performs a time transformation of the equations leading to a new set of governing equations. One of the main limitations attributed to the TI method is that it can only deal with a single-stage (single pitch ratio) but does not suffer either from convergence problems due to the boundary conditions, or requires additional storage, or explicitly makes use of the condition of time periodicity of the flow. However, the method is limited to certain combinations of pitch ratios and rotor velocities, but typical industrial applications for turbomachinery lie within the applicability range. Moreover, it is generally possible to circumvent such limitation by simulating more than a single passage in the reduced domain, yet avoiding the cost of computing the larger directly periodic domain.

To the best of the authors knowledge, this is the first time that the time-inclined method has been implemented in a high-order flux reconstruction method. The combination of the Time-Inclined and the Flux Reconstruction methods is an original solution to tackle the LES and DNS of single-stage turbomachinery

FIGURE 1. NOMENCLATURE AND ILLUSTRATION OF A ROTOR/STATOR PROBLEM WITH DISSIMILAR GAPS.

configurations with dissimilar blade counts. The efficient and accurate solution of this problem will enable the eddy-resolving simulation of at least single-stage configuration, that is a problem that has not been overcome so far.

This paper introduces first the time-inclined method and the high-order numerical scheme of the baseline solver. Then, two-dimensional results in linear cascades of flat plates and low-pressure turbine airfoils are presented. The paper is closed with a discussion of the accuracy of the results and the conclusions.

TIME-INCLINED FORMULATION Euler Equations

The formulation of the time-inclined method has been described previously [14] but is summarised next for the sake of completeness. The two-dimensional Euler equations in the physical coordinate system can be written in conservative form as:

$$h \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (h\mathbf{f})}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial (h\mathbf{g})}{\partial y} = \mathbf{S}, \quad (1)$$

where

$$\mathbf{U} = \begin{pmatrix} \rho \\ \rho u \\ \rho v \\ \rho E \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{f} = \begin{pmatrix} \rho u \\ \rho u^2 + p \\ \rho uv \\ \rho uH \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{g} = \begin{pmatrix} \rho v \\ \rho uv \\ \rho v^2 + p \\ \rho vH \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

and h is the streamtube thickness of the two-dimensional section that gives rise to the source term $\mathbf{S} = (0 \ p h_x \ p h_y \ 0)^T$

in the right-hand side of equation 1. Giles considered a transformation from the physical coordinates (x, y, t) to the computational coordinates (x', y', t') such that periodicity is achieved in the rotor and stator computational domains (see Fig. 1), i.e., $U(x, y, t) = U(x, y + P_r, t + \Delta T)$.

The equations defining the transformation are

$$x' = x, \ y' = y, \ \tau = t - \lambda y \quad (3)$$

where

$$\lambda = \frac{\Delta T}{P_r} = \frac{P_s - P_r}{VP_r}. \quad (4)$$

This transformation can be regarded as a grid mapping analogous to the one that is performed to map the governing equations from the physical domain to the transformed domain in structured solvers. The main difference here is that the time is deemed one more dimension and transformed in the mapping process. The resultant system of equations in the computational coordinate system is,

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}}{\partial \tau} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial x'} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{g}}{\partial y'} = \mathbf{S}, \quad (5)$$

where the new conservation variables are $\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{U} - \lambda \mathbf{g}$. This redefinition of the conservation variables causes a minimum disruption in the baseline numerical method because \mathbf{U} can be calculated from \mathbf{Q} in closed form for a perfect gas. This is particularly useful in GPU based codes where increasing the number of operations per point is computationally forgiven. For explicit codes the main idea is to advance the new conservative variables to the next time step \mathbf{Q}^{n+1} , then compute $\mathbf{U}^{n+1} = F(\mathbf{Q}^{n+1})$, and finally, reevaluate the original physical fluxes in the time instant $(n+1)\Delta t$, i.e. $\mathbf{f}^{n+1} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{U}^{n+1})$ and $\mathbf{g}^{n+1} = \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{U}^{n+1})$.

Departing from the values of $\mathbf{Q} = (q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4)^T$ the relationship between \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{U} can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} q_1 &= \rho(1 - \lambda v) \\ q_2 &= q_1 u \\ q_3 &= q_1 v - \lambda p \\ q_4 &= \frac{1}{2} q_1 (u^2 + v^2) + \frac{1}{\gamma-1} p - \lambda \frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1} p v \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Injecting $u = q_2/q_1$ and $v = (q_3 + \lambda p)/q_1$ from the second and third equations into the fourth equation, the following equation for the static pressure is obtained

$$ap^2 + 2bp + c = 0 \quad (7)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} a &= (\gamma + 1)\lambda^2 \\ b &= -(q_1 - \lambda q_3) \\ c &= (\gamma - 1)(2q_1 q_4 - (q_2^2 + q_3^2)) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The quadratic equation has two solutions

$$p = \frac{1}{a} \left(-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - ac} \right) \quad (9)$$

The negative root yields the correct value for $\lambda \rightarrow 0$. Once p is obtained, the rest of physical variables are easily obtained.

Navier-Stokes Equations

The 2D Navier-Stokes equations that in the physical coordinate system can be written in conservative form as:

$$h \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(h\mathbf{f})}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(h\mathbf{g})}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial(h\mathbf{F})}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(h\mathbf{G})}{\partial y} + \mathbf{S} \quad (10)$$

where

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \tau_{xx} \\ \tau_{yx} \\ \tau_{xx}u + \tau_{xy}v - q_x \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{G} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \tau_{xy} \\ \tau_{yy} \\ \tau_{yx}u + \tau_{yy}v - q_y \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

where the stress tensor is given by

$$\sigma = \mu(\nabla \mathbf{v} + \nabla \mathbf{v}^T) - \frac{2}{3}\mu \mathbf{I} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \quad (12)$$

being μ is the dynamic viscosity, \mathbf{I} , is the identity matrix. The heat flux vector is given by $\mathbf{q} = \kappa \nabla T$, where κ is the conductivity.

The application of the time-inclined transformation to Eq. 10 leads to

$$h \frac{\partial \mathbf{Q}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(h\mathbf{f})}{\partial x'} + \frac{\partial(h\mathbf{g})}{\partial y'} = \frac{\partial(h\mathbf{F})}{\partial x'} + \frac{\partial(h\mathbf{G})}{\partial y'} + \mathbf{S} \quad (13)$$

with $\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{U} - \lambda(\mathbf{g} - \mathbf{G})$. The problem now is that \mathbf{Q} contains temporal and spatial derivatives of \mathbf{U} , and a direct relationship $\mathbf{U} = F(\mathbf{Q})$ does not exist. To circumvent this problem \mathbf{Q} is replaced by $\mathbf{U} - \lambda \mathbf{g}$ which can be shown to be a valid approximation for attached flows at high Reynolds numbers.

NUMERICAL METHOD

Because of computational efficiency, low dissipation schemes are used frequently in scale resolving simulations of turbulent flows instead of standard second-order methods typically used in RANS analysis. Higher-order compact numerical methods such as the Flux Reconstruction method (FR) offer low numerical dissipation and, therefore, are well suited for the simulation of vortical structures and turbulent flows [16].

The time-inclined method has been integrated into a compressible high-order solver [17, 18] based on the FR method of Huynh [19] and extended to triangular elements following the work of Wang and Gao [20]. The method has been successfully used to perform quasi direct numerical simulation of low-pressure turbine transitional flows in the presence of incoming wakes [1, 2]. A summary of the numerical method is given next for the sake of completeness.

Spatial discretization

The FR method [19] for the solution of one-dimensional conservation laws

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (14)$$

is revisited first. Consider a 1D integration domain $\Omega = [0, L]$ discretized in N elements with the i th element defined by $V_i = [x_i, x_{i+1}]$. For each element i we define $p+1$ solution points (SPs) at which the state variable (\mathbf{U}) is evaluated. Given these SPs the solution is approximated using Lagrange polynomials as

$$\mathbf{U}(x, t) \simeq \mathbf{U}_i^h(x, t) = \sum_{j=1}^{p+1} \mathbf{U}_{ij}^h(t) L_j(x) \quad (15)$$

where \mathbf{U}_{ij}^h is the solution at SP j of element i , and $L_j(x)$ is the Lagrange polynomial with value 1 at $x = x_j$. For each element we define a local coordinate, $\xi = [-1, 1]$, such that $x_j = x_i + \frac{\Delta x_i}{2}(\xi_j + 1)$ with $\Delta x_i = x_{i+1} - x_i$. The flux is defined analogously:

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{U}^h) \simeq \mathbf{f}_i^D(\xi, t) = \sum_{j=1}^{p+1} \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{U}_{ij}^h) L_j(\xi) \quad (16)$$

Since the solution is in general discontinuous across element interfaces the flux is reconstructed in such a way that the reconstructed flux $\mathbf{f}^C : i)$ is of degree $p+1$, where p is the order of \mathbf{f}^D ; $ii)$ is close to \mathbf{f}^D ; and $iii)$ takes on the value of the interface fluxes at the boundaries of the element which is computed with a Riemann solver. The final corrected flux is of the form $\mathbf{f}_i^C(\xi) = \mathbf{f}_i^D(\xi) + \gamma_i(\xi)$ where $\gamma_i(\xi)$ is the correction flux function defined as:

$$\gamma_i(\xi) = [\mathbf{f}_L^f - \mathbf{f}^D(\xi = -1)] g_L(\xi) + [\mathbf{f}_R^f - \mathbf{f}^D(\xi = 1)] g_R(\xi) \quad (17)$$

where \mathbf{f}_L^f and \mathbf{f}_R^f are the left and right interface fluxes, and $g_L(\xi)$ and $g_R(\xi)$ are the left and right correction functions. The correction functions are chosen as the left and right Radau polynomials in this work to recover the nodal-based discontinuous Galerkin formulation. The discrete form of Eq. 14 is:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \frac{d\xi}{dx} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{p+1} \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{U}_{ij}^h) \frac{dL_j}{d\xi}(\xi) + \right. \\ \left. [\mathbf{f}_L^f - \mathbf{f}^D(\xi = -1)] \frac{dg_L}{d\xi}(\xi) + \right. \\ \left. [\mathbf{f}_R^f - \mathbf{f}^D(\xi = 1)] \frac{dg_R}{d\xi}(\xi) \right\} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

which is advanced in time using a fourth-order Runge-Kutta scheme.

The extension to multiple dimensions of the method is readily done for quadrilateral elements as tensor product operations in multiple dimensions. Since all derivative operations are made on the standard element ($\xi = [-1, 1]$ and $\eta = [-1, 1]$) equation 14 is rewritten in the standard element as:

$$J \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{f}}(\mathbf{U})}{\partial \xi} + \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{g}}(\mathbf{U})}{\partial \eta} = 0 \quad (19)$$

with

$$\tilde{\mathbf{f}}(\mathbf{U}) = J(\xi_x \mathbf{f} + \xi_y \mathbf{g}), \text{ and } \tilde{\mathbf{g}}(\mathbf{U}) = J(\eta_x \mathbf{f} + \eta_y \mathbf{g}) \quad (20)$$

where J is the determinant of the jacobian matrix and, ξ_x, ξ_y, η_x and η_y are the elements of the inverse of the jacobian matrix. The final discretized form becomes now:

$$\begin{aligned}
J \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \sum_{m=0}^p \sum_{n=0}^p (\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{mn}^D L'_m(\xi) L_n(\eta) + \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{mn}^U L_m(\xi) L'_n(\eta)) \\
+ [\tilde{\mathbf{f}}'_L - \tilde{\mathbf{f}}(-1, \eta)] g'_L(\xi) + [\tilde{\mathbf{f}}'_R - \tilde{\mathbf{f}}(1, \eta)] g'_R(\xi) \\
+ [\tilde{\mathbf{g}}'_D - \tilde{\mathbf{g}}(\xi, -1)] g'_L(\eta) + [\tilde{\mathbf{g}}'_U - \tilde{\mathbf{g}}(\xi, 1)] g'_R(\eta) = 0
\end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where the subscripts D and U denote ‘‘down’’ and ‘‘upper’’ sides, respectively. The extension of the method to triangular elements is performed using the Correction Procedure by Reconstruction (CPR) approach of (author?) [20] that is not described here for the sake of brevity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Several test cases have been conducted to assess the accuracy of the implementation and the approach. Two two-dimensional linear cascades of plates and T106 [21] airfoils have been chosen as testing vehicles.

Flat Plate Linear Cascade

A linear cascade of flat plates with zero stagger angle and a pitch to chord ratio of $P_s/c = 0.5$ has been used to test the implementation. The exit Mach number of the cascade is $M_2 = 0.39$ and the incidence is null. The cascade has a finite thickness t to ease the mesh generation process ($t/c = 1.5\%$). The plate is considered as the rotor passing situated downstream of a row of stators with pitch P_s . The ratio between the number of stators, N_s , and rotors, N_r , is $N_s/N_r = 15/6$, and therefore the simulation does not fit into a single passage. The computational domain of a full annulus (the directly periodic domain) simulation consists of six plates in this particular case. The domain is discretised using a hybrid grid of 4th-order triangles and quads. The equivalent second-order mesh consists of 100 points on the plate and 20 in the leading- and trailing edges. The boundary layer regions is discretised with 4 quad layers (16 points in the 4th-order mesh), and the whole mesh totals 13,500 cells per passage. A sinusoidal perturbation of 2.5% of the inlet total pressure is imposed at the inlet, giving rise to a mix of pressure, vortical and entropy waves. The dimensionless speed of the rotor is $M_r = 0.52$. The combination of the rotor speed and the number of perturbations gives rise to a high blade-passing reduced frequency $k = \omega c/v_{2,is} = 40.4$. See Fig. 2 (a) for a general description of the setup.

Figure 2 (b) compares the normalized modulus (normalized amplitude of the complex unsteady perturbations) of the first harmonic of the static pressure $|\hat{p}'_1|$ on the lower side of the plate obtained by a full annulus analysis and the time-inclined method. The static pressure can be expressed as the sum of a mean flow and an unsteady perturbation,

(A) Real part of the vertical velocity

(B) Modulus of the 1st harmonic of the unsteady pressure on the plate lower side

FIGURE 2. FIRST HARMONIC OF THE VERTICAL VELOCITY (A) AND COMPARISON BETWEEN THE UNSTEADY PRESSURE ON THE LOWER SIDE OF THE FLAT PLATE OBTAINED WITH AN INVISCID FULL ANNULUS ANALYSIS AND THE TIME-INCLINED METHOD (B) ($M_2 = 0.39, P_r/P_s = 15/6, M_r = 0.52, i = 0^\circ, P_r/c = 0.5, k = \omega c/v_{2,is} = 40.4$)

$$p(x, y, t) = \bar{p}(x, y) + p'(x, y, t) = \bar{p}(x, y) + \text{Re}(\hat{p}'_n e^{j2\pi\omega_n t}), \quad (22)$$

where \hat{p}'_n is the n -th complex Fourier coefficient of the pressure.

It can be seen that the degree of agreement between both approaches is very high. It must be recalled at this point that for inviscid flows, the time-inclined method is exact. The differences are due to small differences in the numerics. In this case, the

FIGURE 3. FIRST HARMONIC OF THE MODULUS OF THE STATIC PRESSURE FOR THE INVISCID AND VISCOUS CASES (A) AND COMPARISON BETWEEN THE UNSTEADY PRESSURE ON THE LOWER SIDE OF THE FLAT PLATE OBTAINED WITH A VISCOUS FULL ANNULUS ANALYSIS AND THE TIME-INCLINED METHOD (B) ($M_2 = 0.39$, $P_r/P_s = 15/6$, $M_r = 0.52$, $i = 0^\circ$, $P_r/c = 0.5$, $k = \omega c/v_{2,is} = 40.4$)

dimensionless parameter of the time-inclined method is $\lambda a_0 = 0.385$.

Figure 4 shows the distribution of the modulus of the second and third harmonic of the unsteady pressure on the lower side of the flat plate. The solid lines correspond to the full-annulus analysis, also name Physical Plane (PP), whereas the time-inclined

FIGURE 4. SECOND AND THIRD HARMONIC OF THE UNSTEADY PRESSURE ON THE LOWER SIDE OF THE FLAT PLATE OBTAINED WITH AN INVISCID FULL ANNULUS ANALYSIS AND THE TIME-INCLINED METHOD. ($M_2 = 0.39$, $P_r/P_s = 15/6$, $M_r = 0.52$, $i = 0^\circ$, $P_r/c = 0.5$, $k = \omega c/v_{2,is} = 40.4$)

(TI) plane solution is represented with symbols. The level of agreement is an indication that the solution is converged. There are some local discrepancies in the displayed solutions in the higher harmonics. This is as expected since the higher the harmonic, the higher is the influence of the numerical errors. However, the matching is deemed excellent.

The same configuration was computed retaining the viscous terms. The Reynolds number based on the flat plate chord is $Re_c = 1.1 \times 10^5$. The first observation is that the unsteady pressure fields created due to the interaction of the wake with the plate leading edge are different (see Fig. 3 (a)). The modulus of the unsteady pressure patterns are alike, but it can be observed that close to the plate there is a short-wavelength oscillation caused by vortex shedding in the leading-edge region. The same behaviour can be observed in the first harmonic of the unsteady pressure distribution on the plate as well (Fig. 3 (b)). The comparison between the full-domain and time-inclined method is displayed in Fig. 3 (b). It can be noticed that though both curves are alike, the agreement is not as good as in the inviscid case. However, at the front and rear of the plate, the matching is good.

The most likely root cause of the error is that a direct relationship between the transformed and the conservative variables, $\mathbf{U} = F(\mathbf{Q})$, does not exist for the Navier-Stokes equations and therefore the resulting set of equations is approximated. How-

FIGURE 5. COMPARISON OF THE MEAN ISENTROPIC MACH NUMBER DISTRIBUTION (A) AND THE 1st HARMONIC OF THE UNSTEADY PRESSURE ABOUT THE T106 (B) BETWEEN THE FULL ANNULUS ANALYSIS AND THE TIME-INCLINED METHOD. ($M_{2,is} = 0.39$, $P_r/P_s = 15/6$, $M_r = 0.52$, $\alpha_{in} = 37.7^\circ$, $P_r/c = 0.798$, $k = \omega c/v_{2,is} = 26.4$)

ever, as it will be shown in the next sub-section, its impact on a LPT airfoil is much smaller than in the case of a flat plate (see Fig. 6(b)).

T106 LPT Linear Cascade

The T106 airfoil [21] has been chosen as the vehicle to test the time-inclined method in a realistic configuration. The isentropic exit Mach number, $M_{2,is} = 0.39$, the rotor Mach number, $M_r = 0.52$, and the ratio between the rotor and the stator pitch, $P_r/P_s = 15/6$, are the same as in the flat plate case. The Reynolds number of this case based on the chord and the exit velocity is $Re_c = 1.1 \times 10^5$. A sinusoidal perturbation of 2.5% of the inlet total pressure has been imposed at the inflow. The computational domain is discretised using a hybrid grid of 4th-order triangles and quads. The equivalent second-order mesh (See Fig. 5 (a)) consists of 150 points on the airfoil and 8 quad layers to account for the boundary layer region, totalling 7,600 triangular cells and 3,200 quad cells per passage. The 4th order mesh has 16 Degrees of Freedom (DOF) per quad and 10 DOF per triangle.

Figure 5 (b) plots the 1st harmonic of the entropy to give an overall idea of the case. It can be observed how the incoming wakes propagate undistorted through the inlet uniform field, and then are distorted by the mean flow within the passage. A slight separation can be observed in the rear part of the suc-

tion side, both in the Mach number snapshot (Fig. 5 (a)) and in the entropy field (Fig. 5 (b)). The separation region is very small due to the high reduced frequency of the incoming wakes ($k = \omega c/v_{2,is} = 26.4$) that tend to suppress the steady separation. This phenomenon is exactly as described by (author?) [2] but in a much finer and three-dimensional grid.

Figure 6 (a) displays the mean isentropic Mach number distribution obtained by a viscous full annulus analysis (6 passages) and the time-inclined method. It can be noticed that the matching between both is nearly perfect. The separation point, which is located at about 90% of the axial chord, is hardly visible. The case with steady inflow (solid red line) exhibits a longer bubble that reattaches closer to the trailing-edge than the case with unsteady inflow. Moreover, the pressure side is slightly different as well.

Figure 6 (b) shows the distribution of the first harmonic of the unsteady pressure on the airfoil. The first observation is that the highest level of unsteadiness is located in the rear part of the suction side, where a closed and thin recirculating bubble can be seen. The shedding of this bubble gives rise to high unsteadiness. The second is that the agreement between the time-inclined approach and the full-domain simulation is very high. This degree of matching is essentially the same for all the variables.

A comparison between the directly periodic and single passage simulations is shown in Fig. 7. There are two single passage simulations. The first is performed with the TI method matching

(A) MEAN ISENTROPIC MACH NUMBER

(B) UNSTEADY PRESSURE 1ST HARMONIC (VISCIOUS CASE)

FIGURE 6. COMPARISON OF THE MEAN ISENTROPIC MACH NUMBER DISTRIBUTION (A) AND THE 1st HARMONIC OF THE UNSTEADY PRESSURE ABOUT THE T106 (B) BETWEEN THE FULL ANNULUS ANALYSIS AND THE TIME-INCLINED METHOD FOR THE VISCIOUS CASE. ($M_{2,is} = 0.39$, $P_r/P_s = 15/6$, $M_r = 0.52$, $\alpha_{in} = 37.7^\circ$, $P_r/c = 0.798$, $k = \omega c/v_{2,is} = 26.4$, $Re_c = 1.1 \times 10^5$)

the blade count and reduced frequency of the directly periodic domain. The second employs the baseline code approximating the pitch ratio between the rotor and stator to three, instead of using the exact $P_r/P_s=15/6$, and decreasing the velocity of the rotor to match the reduced frequency of the original problem.

Figure 7 (a) compares the modulus of the first harmonic of the unsteady pressure obtained by the three methods. The agreement between the TI method and the full-annulus solution is better than with the case with the approximate blade count. This is especially true for the areas close to the leading and trailing edges. The same observation can be made about the T106 cascade in the inviscid simulations shown in figure 7 (b), where the TI method matches the full-annulus solution very well, but the single passage approximation grossly mispredicts the fundamental harmonic of the unsteady pressure.

It is concluded that both for the flat plate and the T106 cases the Time-Inclined method does a good replicating the acoustics of the linear cascade, not only in the inviscid cases, where the TI method is exact, but in the viscous cases where the TI is approximated. The matching for the T106 is much better than for the flat plate case. This is attributed to the cascade loading since the Reynolds number is essentially the same for both cases. In the flat plate case, the unsteadiness is caused by the interaction of a vortical gust with the leading-edge where actually the flow exhibits a discontinuity, whereas for the T106 case, the unsteadiness is caused due to the interaction of the gust with a non-uniform flow-field. The two mechanisms are essentially different, and the role of the viscous terms in the description of the flow about the flat plate leading-edge seems dominant. However, this test case is deemed not relevant in realistic applications.

Finally, Fig. 8 shows a snapshot of the first harmonic of the unsteady pressure. The case is equivalent to having 15 stators in front of 6 rotors. A cut-off potential perturbation is clearly seen at the inlet. The suction side exhibits a strong unsteadiness caused by a local separation. This unsteadiness is synchronised with the inlet perturbation. This local unsteadiness is captured as well by the time-inclined method.

Computational cost considerations

There are four main factors that contribute to the different computational cost between the TI and directly periodic simulations

1. COST PER TIME-STEP

The TI method requires the computation of the conservative variables from the transformed variables after each substep of the Runge-Kutta scheme representing a negligible additional cost per time-step.

2. TIME-STEP LIMITATION DUE TO NUMERICAL STABILITY

The time-step size in TI plane is more restrictive than in the physical plane, as can be deduced from the magnitude

(A) MODULUS OF THE 1ST HARMONIC OF THE UNSTEADY PRESSURE ON THE PLATE LOWER SIDE (VISCOUS CASE)

(B) UNSTEADY PRESSURE 1ST HARMONIC ON THE T106 PROFILE (INVISCID CASE)

FIGURE 7. COMPARISON BETWEEN THE FULL ANNULUS ANALYSIS AND THE TIME-INCLINED METHOD OF THE 1st HARMONIC OF THE UNSTEADY PRESSURE ABOUT A FLAT PLATE (A) AND A T106 LINEAR CASCADE ($M_{2, is} = 0.39, \alpha_{in} = 37.7^\circ, P_r/c = 0.798, k = \omega c/v_{2, is} = 26.4, Re_c = 1.1 \times 10^5$) ($P_r/P_s = 15/6, M_r = 0.52$) AND A SINGLE PASSAGE WITH MATCHING REDUCED FREQUENCY AND INEXACT PITCH RATIO ($P_r/P_s = 3, M_r = 0.43$).

FIGURE 8. SNAPSHOT OF THE OF THE REAL PART OF THE FIRST HARMONIC OF THE STATIC PRESSURE OF A VISCOUS SOLUTION ABOUT THE T106 AIRFOILS ($p_s/c = 0.8, M_e = 0.39, P_s/P_R = 6/15$, ROTOR MACH NUMBER $M_r = 0.52$, REYNOLDS NUMBER $Re = 10^5$)

of the eigenvalues of the linearized transformed equations. The severity of this restriction depends on the transformation parameter λ . The larger the absolute value of λ , the smaller the maximum time step. In other words, the maximum stable time step decreases as the pitch disparity increases or as the rotor velocity decreases (see Eq. (4)).

3. NUMBER OF DEGREES OF FREEDOM (DOF)

The main purpose of the TI method is to reduce the size of the directly periodic computational domain. Such reduction has a direct impact on the computational cost since the reduced domain contains fewer DOFs, thus reducing the number of operations per time-step and the memory requirements.

4. CONVERGENCE TIME TO THE PERIODIC OR QUASI-PERIODIC STATE

While the physical convergence time depends solely on the reduced frequency and the blade count, the convergence of harmonic methods depends as well on the details of the numerical implementation of the boundary conditions that may delay convergence [12, 22]. Since the TI method does not require additional modelling (at least in the inviscid cases) no penalty is expected from the TI to converge to the final state.

A thorough quantitative explanation of the relative cost of the

TI method is out of the scope of this work, but it can be safely said that the computational cost is at most the same as that of the baseline time marching method but on a much smaller computational domain. The main difficulty in quantifying the method lies setting up the full annulus simulations in realistic cases, and the determination of the convergence of the simulation since the high-order method tends to develop non-synchronous unsteadiness even in the presence of a synchronous excitation. This work is postponed to a future dedicated paper.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The time-inclined method has been implemented for the first time in a high-order flux reconstruction method and applied to account for dissimilar gaps in rotor/stator interaction problems. The results for two linear cascades of airfoils have been presented.

A linear cascade of flat-plates has been subject to a sinusoidal gust of total pressure. The inviscid results compare very well with the full-annulus simulations whereas the matching of the viscous case is not as good. The differences are associated firstly with the difficulties in performing accurate simulations of flat plates since the mean flow is uniform and the unsteady solution is prone to magnify errors, and the intrinsic inaccuracies of the time-inclined approach to deal with viscous flows.

A cascade of T106 airfoils with similar inlet conditions to the flat plate case has been simulated at representative Reynolds numbers. The matching, in this case, is better than for the cascade of flat plates. The agreement of the mean solution and the first harmonic with the full-domain simulation is very good.

Because of the results presented here, it is concluded that the method must be further pursued and applied to more demanding cases of industrial interest. Future works will address the accuracy of viscous eddy-resolving simulations where the wavelengths of the unsteadiness are very short and the impact of viscous terms can be higher.

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